

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the dissertation, entitled "Evaluation on the inhibitory effect of methanolic leaf extract of *Hemidesmus indicus* on Jab1 in MDA MB-231 breast cancer cell line" submitted to Bharthiar University, in partial fulfillment of the degree of 'Master of Science in Medical Biotechnology', is a record of the original research done by Mr. Akash Deep, During February 2020 – June 2022 to him study in the plant Molecular Biology Laboratory, Department of Biotechnology at Bharthiar University under my guidance. The dissertation has not formed the basis for the award of any Degree/ Diploma Associate ship/ Fellowship or any other similar title to any candidate of any other University.

Place: Coimbatore

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17.06.22

Signature of the Guide

Dr. M. ARUN, M.Sc., Ph.D.,
Assistant Professor
Department of Biotechnology
Bharthiar University
Coimbatore - 641 046, Tamilnadu, India

Head of the Department

Signature of the Co - Guide

External Examiner

Dr. G. SUDHANDIRAN
Professor
Department of Biochemistry
University of Madras
Guindy Campus, Chennai - 600 025.